

Assessment of the Impact of Temperature on Regional and Global Biodiversity: a Meta-Analysis

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Introduction

Global and regional average temperature have changed and is predicted to change more in coming decades. This is partially explained by natural cycle and human activities. This change is affecting species suitable habitat, species richness and species density within communities. The effect of this change on biodiversity has been widely discussed where peer-review publications have become the principal vessel to share the gained knowledge, however, the overall effect to different species categories is not yet clear. To this end, statistical methods that allow us to summarize and synthesize the knowledge points from literature are needed. We hereby aim to investigate the overall effect of the rise of temperature (T) on biodiversity using a meta-analysis approach.

Methodology

A meta-analysis is a statistical approach which allows us to synthesize and generalize the gained knowledge points from literature, and to develop and test the overarching hypotheses. We computed the effect size (R) as the log ratio of the means in two states (e.g. Treat and control). We used Z-test to test the significance of the total heterogeneity (Q) [1]. Based on the work of Houwelingen and colleagues, we parametrize the random (REM) and mixed effect model (MEM).

Data collection

We collected 100 published articles from which 2080 cases assessing the effect of ambient temperature change on different species have been extracted. We did not limit the search on any given interval of time. We quantified the effect of T with respect to suitable habitat, density, species richness and biomass. We used 11 species taxonomic, grouped studies with respect to the continent where the study has been carried out, to the methodology used (observation/modelling) and the effect to species with/without dispersal capacity.

Main conclusion

- Some taxonomic groups are negatively affected by the temperature rise, whilst others seem to be robust to temperature change (Fig. 1).
- Eurasia, Australia and Indian Ocean are locations most affected by the rise of temperature (Fig. 2).
- Among the four species attributes considered here, species richness and suitable habitat are the two most sensitive attributes affected by the rising temperature (Fig. 3).
- Considering species' dispersal capacity when assessing the effect of temperature rise gives a better estimate than ignoring species' dispersal capacity (Fig. 4).
- Of the methods used in conducting assessment, results from modelling approach obviously exaggerate the reality found in observational studies (Fig. 5).

References

[1] Michael Borenstein et al., *Introduction to meta-analysis*. Chichester, West Sussex, U.K.: John Wiley & Sons, 2009.

Results

Figure 1: Mixed effect model on species classification

Figure 2: Mixed effect model on study location

Figure 3: Mixed effect model on species attributes

Figure 4: Mixed effect model on species dispersal capacity

Figure 5: Mixed effect model on methodology